

Towards an Alternative Conception of “Home” in Anglophone Naga Fiction¹

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Abstract

Anglophone Naga literature is an emerging literary phenomenon in the Northeast of India. Behind its swift rise to visibility in the region is the important space it provides for discourse on a wide range of issues in contemporary Naga society. In this article, the evolving idea of home in Naga society is explored via the works of Easterine Kire – especially *When the River Sleeps*. The article delineates and contends that the alterity of Kire’s notion of home lies in its digression from the traditional idea of home in Naga culture, which has the territoriality of the village of one’s birth as a necessary precondition for imagining a home. Instead, a fluid, mental concept of home is presented by Kire, indicating a major shift in attitude with respect to the notion of home in millennial Naga society.

Keywords: Naga, Easterine Kire, Northeast India, ecocriticism, decoloniality, home.

Anglophone Naga Fiction at a Glance

The history of Anglophone Naga fiction is barely twenty years old. But in two decades, it has witnessed a slew of experiments with forms and modes of literary expression to become a visible literary constituency in India’s geopolitical and cultural periphery. Currently, in 2024,

¹ “Anglophone” is a better term for categorising the phenomenon of Naga writing in English as it is evocative of the colonial experience of the Nagas, and the impact it had on their history, culture, and language.

there are over thirty published works of fiction written in English by Nagas.² In 2003, the first novel was published by the non-profit Ura Academy based in Kohima, and distributed locally and/or through personal contacts. It was authored by Easterine Kire and titled as *A Naga Village Remembered*, referring to the Angami village of Khonoma near Kohima.³ The creative retelling is based on true events and the experience of the people of Khonoma in the wake of their encounter with the British in the nineteenth century. Shortly after, in 2005, the late Temsula Ao published her critically-acclaimed collection of short stories, *These Hills Called Home: Stories From a War Zone*, in which generic elements of realism, historical fiction, and psychological realism are combined to weave stories of resistance, trauma, and hope that took place during the Naga people's most tumultuous period from the 1950s to the 1980s. Kire's *A Terrible Matriarchy* (2007) was the next major publication. A coming-of-age novel of the protagonist, Delieno's story is narrated against the backdrop of an evolving Naga society in Kohima, mired, as it were, in Naga insurgency of the 1960s and the 1970s. Next to be published was Ao's anthology of eight short stories called *Laburnum for My Head* (2009), which are written in the mould of traditional realism with the evolving post-colonial Naga society as their background. Despite its relative brevity, the anthology was awarded the Sahitya Akademi Award for English in 2013. Then, in 2010, Kire published an (auto)biographical novel of the eponymous *Mari*, which vividly chronicles "her" (via Kire's authorial voice) experience of the Japanese invasion of Kohima in 1944 and after. Kire followed this up with another novel about Naga insurgency, *Bitter Wormwood* (2011), narrated from the perspective of the protagonist, Mose. These are some of the major works of

² This figure is on the lower side of the estimate.

³ The novel has been re-issued in 2018 by Speaking Tiger with an added title *Sky Is My Father: A Naga Village Remembered*. After her first novel in 2003, Easterine reverted to using her maiden name "Kire" instead of "Iralu".

fiction by Nagas that paved the way for the emergence of Anglophone Naga literature as a visible regional category within the broad rubric of Indian literature.⁴

In the first decade of Anglophone Naga fiction (2003-2013), the modes and forms of literary expression used for representing and/or redescribing Naga experience were fairly limited to historical fiction, realism, and (auto)biographies. And the dominant themes of these works too largely centred on and around the experience of the Naga people (both individual and collective) during the peak of their separatist movement against the Indian state (1950s to the 1980s). Perhaps realising the danger of Anglophone Naga fiction being perceived or stereotyped as *only* about insurgency and/or resistance, and motivated by the desire to forge a new mode of literary expression that could represent more fully the full breath of Naga imaginative culture and lifeworld, Kire wrote her next major novel, *When The River Sleeps* (2014; *WTRS* henceforth),⁵ in a refreshingly bold and experimental mode. She combined Novalis' *magical idealism* with what I'd call "Naga realism" to inaugurate a new mode of literary representation unseen before in Naga literature. By "Naga realism", I mean a mode of creative rendering that is natural to the Naga lived-reality, and one which does not involve or require a literary contrivance. For example, sightings of the spirit of the dead and/or hearing/sensing their presence (*A Terrible Matriarchy*), and some other meta-phenomena that are found in *WTRS* and Naga literature generally, are not alien to Naga reality. But to the non-Naga reader, these instances may be "misread" as fantastic or conforming to the postcolonial language of magic realism. Therefore, the prefix "Naga" to realism, as in Naga realism, offers a conceptual distinction between "magical" elements that are entirely

⁴ These works were all published in Delhi by trade publishers and widely distributed.

⁵ This novel has been translated into Norwegian as *Mens Elva Sover* (2018) by Orkana. The novel is also available in Korean and Kannada translations – as informed to me by Kire herself in a recent email conversation. However, neither of us could recall/find the title or name of the translator in these languages at the time of submitting this article.

commensurate with Naga reality and those that are outside it. For the fantastical elements in Naga literature that are designedly exaggerated even for Naga readerly sensibility, and are therefore *outside* the conceptual scope of Naga realism, Novalis' magical idealism or the postcolonial magic realism are more appropriate concepts: Kire's *Son of the Thundercloud* (2016) is an example of low-grade fantasy, as are some of the elements in *WTRS, Journey of the Stone* (2021), *Spirit Night* (2022), etc. Perhaps because of this breakthrough in form and mode of literary expression in Naga fiction, *WTRS* received great attention from both Naga and non-Naga readers. It also won Kire The Hindu Literary Prize for 2015.

All About Home

Apart from the experiment with the form of literary expression, *WTRS* is also notable for its exploration (obliquely though) of an emerging theme in contemporary Naga discourse: home. Kire revisits this theme through the figure of the nomad (Pele) in her novella, *Son of the Thundercloud*,⁶ which won the Sahitya Bal Puraskar 2018. In fact, the idea of home as a thematic principle for organising and representing Naga experience is not recent to Naga literature. In *These Hills Called Home*, Temsula Ao uses home ironically (and tinged with sarcasm) to chronicle the unviable state of Naga ancestral homeland for making a "home" in the 1950s all through to the 1970s – courtesy of the Naga separatist movement. Ao's notion of home, as well as Kire's till *WTRS*, is underpinned by conformity to the village-of-birth precondition for imagining home in traditional Naga culture. In a recently published anthology of poetry, *A Country With No Home: Poems from JNU* (2024), Lozaan Khumbah, a Naga poet-scholar from Manipur, too deploys a similar notion of "home" as the hermeneutical principle for the different sentiments of his poems. The perceived "lack" of a

⁶ The novella has been translated into Hindi by Poonam Jain and published by Speaking Tiger Books (2024).

territorially viable village (country) for building a “home” underscores his poetic lamentation. Khumbah’s poetic location is similar to Temsula Ao in *These Hills Called Home*. In the words of an early Naga reviewer, who was a fellow scholar of the poet at Jawaharlal Nehru University:

If one were to identify a strand that runs through almost all the poems in *A Country With No Home*, it would be the feeling of being unsettled. Perhaps, it was the intention of the author to unsettle the mind of the reader. And yet, there is something so sincere and honest in the poems that one cannot help but think that it is the author who is unsettled and the words merely convey his state of mind; like the little pebble drifting with the current going everywhere, reaching nowhere; or the restless spirit haunting people’s homes without finding its own. The poems yearn for home but refuses to settle for a home. And so, you have a poem like “Ghost” wanting to belong to a home and then “Sons of the Soil” which begins with the line “Home is not for me”. And yet, this tormenting, and dare I say contradicting, feelings about home are so haunting and come across so forcefully that it is to me the major takeaway of *A Country With No Home*.⁷

Against the backdrop of this emergent thematic concern with “home” in Naga literary discourse, this article explores an alternative notion of home in *WTRS*, embodied, as it were, “obliquely”, in the text. The article delineates and contends that Kire’s alternative conception offers a destabilising perspective on the rigid monopoly that Naga tradition has over the idea of *what* and *where* home should be. The novelty of Kire’s alternative notion lies in its

⁷ Thejalhoukho Casavi, “Reading *A Country with No Home*”. 21 August 2024, *Nagaland Post*.

capacity to imagine home *outside* the village – particularly of one’s birth.⁸ Thematically, home does not appear to be a “major” concern in *WRTS*, even though it underpins much of the unarticulated motive for character movement. In fact, it is one of the least “visible” themes, glossed over by the surface-level preoccupation with the adventures of the protagonist, Villie, and the cultural setting of the narrative. Unsurprisingly, literary commentators pass over it when the novel is taken up for study. Some of these readings in recent times range from ethnographic fiction to environmental humanities (Roderick Wijunamai),⁹ and ecocriticism (Achingliu Kamei)¹⁰ to decolonial fiction (Baishya and Kalita-Moral).¹¹ It has also been very generously labelled as a work that is at the “frontline of contemporary indigenous literature” by Vivek Menezes.¹² Such readings are certainly not

⁸ Matrilineal residence is not unheard of in patriarchal and patrilineal Naga society. But it is more of an exception than a norm.

⁹ “Understanding Naga Cosmology Through Easterine Kire’s Fictional Narratives.” *Keeper of Stories: Critical Readings of Easterine Kire’s Novels*, edited by Veio Pou, Maine, Highlander, 2023, pp.29-42.

¹⁰ “An Ecocritical Study of Easterine Kire’s *When The River Sleeps* and *Son of the Thundercloud*.” *Keeper of Stories: Critical Readings of Easterine Kire’s Novels*, edited by Veio Pou, Maine, Highlander, 2023, pp. 201-214.

¹¹ A.K. Baishya and Rakhee Kalita Moral “Insides-Outsides: Northeast Anglophone Literature”. *South Asian Review*, 2023, pp. 180-190. With respect to Naga literature and decoloniality, the exonym “Naga” is unthinkable without British intervention. From existing as independent village polities locked in internecine blood feuds in the centuries before the British arrived to their homeland in the 19th century, the constituting tribes of the ethnopolitical group “Naga” had no conception of ethnicity in their tribal languages. Historically, their identities were primarily village-based and/or clan-based. In fact, it may even be argued that the tribal identities of the Nagas were forged individually only after the European missionaries introduced western education to them and linguistic identities were forged simultaneously with the creation of a Prestige language in/for a given tribal group – that too mostly initiated by European missionaries. Most of the individual Naga tribes were speaking multiple dialects (sometimes village dialects that were not mutually intelligible) without an “official” language when they encountered the European missionaries. So, the premise and objective of decoloniality – which is to “decolonise” a culture of “foreign” (European) influence/heritage in its many iterative forms – would invariably involve the deconstruction of “Naga” itself, if we are to be intellectually honest. The reification of “Naga” as a sociocultural entity in essentialist terms in the 20th and 21st centuries cannot erase or hide its history of construction and the fundamental role of colonial ethnography and taxonomies in this decades-long process. In fact, whatever putative meaning “Naga” may have acquired today, it is intellectually impossible to imagine the term without colonial intervention. We have to be honest about that when engaging in any form of revisionist historiography – cultural, social, political.

¹² “Naga Writer Easterine Kire’s Clear Bright Sound Over a Sleeping World.” *Scroll*, 20 May 2021. “Indigenous” or “indigeneity” as a concept and term of identity in the Indian context is not without controversy, especially because of its deployment by those who identify with it for political and legal objectives. There are some research articles by Naga scholars that are under publication which are critical of the use of “indigeneity” in the Naga context. But for the larger debate on the issue in the Indian context, refer to Andre Beteille, “The Idea of Indigenous People.” *Current Anthropology*, Vol. 9, No. 2, April 1998, pp. 187-192; Virginius Xaxa, “Tribes as Indigenous People of India.” *Economic and Political Weekly*, Vol. 34, No. 51, Dec. 18-24, 1999, pp. 3589-

unwarranted by the text, as Kire's characters and the world they inhabit are distinctly Naga, and therefore, the realism embodied, perforce, are open to Levi-Strauss' *thick description* (with multifocal resonances, one might add). But perhaps we need to be more circumspect about the interpretive frameworks and theoretical paradigms we choose for reading or studying *WTRS*, or Naga literature for that matter. Otherwise, the risk of shoehorning a text or novel into a preexisting theoretical fit is high given the newness of Naga literature, especially fiction, and the lack of a corresponding tradition of literary criticism to draw insights from.

For instance, the category "ethnographic fiction" for *WTRS* appears to be a case of misplaced reading. Ethnography is a pre-requisite of any good realist fiction. The coordinates of place, time, and people (culture) are what give the characters (and the author) a reference point and context for engaging with the thematic concerns of the narrative. The fact of the matter is that the *ethnographicity* of Kire's *WTRS* is an *aesthetic* requirement and not a methodological abstraction meant to produce knowledge – of the "objective" or scientific kind. It is a common feature of literary *worldling* meant to make the narrative relatable and/or believable. A similar reevaluation is also necessary for ecocritical readings of *WTRS*. As a critical paradigm and/or framework for interpretation, ecocriticism is ideologically grounded in environmental discourse and its politics. *WTRS* is essentially set in a forest that is owned by the Nagas in a pre-Christian context, so the interface with nature is naturally framed by animistic beliefs. The general principles that underpin Naga interaction with nature in the novel can certainly be extrapolated into a (viable) worldview, but it should not be therefore presumed as emanating from ecocritical concerns. Such a tendency is an example of *eisegesis* in hermeneutics, where one reads one's meaning into a text. And though one may argue for

3595; and N.K. Das, "Indigeneity, Anthropology and the Indian Tribes: A Critique." *Journal of Adivasi and Indigenous Tribes*, Vol. II, No.1, Feb. 2015, pp.11-34.

multiple meanings, and even bracket out authorial intention in the interpretation of a text – in the manner of the New Critics and the structuralism of Roland Barthes¹³ – such an approach runs counter to the purpose of good criticism.¹⁴ Authorial intention in relation to the executed textual form and content have always been the basis of good criticism. In a recent literature festival in Nagaland, Kire lamented the general tendency of critics, both Naga and non-Naga, to “misread” her works in order to fit pre-existing ideological frames and narratives.¹⁵ My own view is that a purely postmodernist approach to a writer like Kire can negate and strip the particularity of her authorial voice. And if forging a global literary commons is the direction in which literary humanities is headed, or should be headed, it is imperative that we seek out and preserve authorial intention in the many meanings of their texts.

Returning to the theme of home in *WTRS*, a close reading of the principal characters reveals the abstracted idea of home as a determining factor in the exercise of agency. Kire does not give a name to this emergent idea of home, but she delineates it through the actions and poignant remarks of her principal characters, Vilie, Ate, and Zote. Very early in the novel, Kire introduces a Nepali couple as possessing a mobile notion of home due to economic reasons (13). They are not “rooted” to a particular location, and so their idea of “home” is where they are at the moment. They are a family that is constantly relocating and with no articulated sense of a “final” home to where they could return once their economic sojourn in a “foreign” land is over. And it is precisely this lack of a fixed notion of home

¹³ Roland Barthes, “The Death of the Author”. *Image, Music, Text*. Translated by Stephen Heath, Hill & Wang, 1977, pp. 142-148. Willingham, John, “The New Criticism: Then and Now.” *Contemporary Literary Theory*, edited by Douglas Atkins and Janice Morrow, University of Massachusetts Press, 1989, pp.24-41.

¹⁴ See William Irwin (ed.). *The Death and Resurrection of the Author*. Greenwood Press, 2002; and Sean Burke. *The Death and Return of the Author. Criticism and Subjectivity in Barthes, Foucault, and Derrida*. Edinburgh University Press, 2008.

¹⁵ *The White Owl Literature Festival & Book Fair*. Held from 9 February to 10 February 2024 in Dimapur. Easterine Kire was the Keynote Speaker.

which allows the Nepali couple to remain “detached” from *a* place. They represent the figure of the nomad to interrogate, or even demystify, the presumption of place in the construction of home. For the Nepali couple, homelessness does not really mean a “lack” or “absence” as is generally and immediately assumed in Naga culture. Rather, it is simply a mode of living. Nomadism as a mode of living for the Nepali couple in *WTRS* is not characterised as an inability to reach a final destination and a home. Instead, it functions as an epistemic contrast to the traditional Naga way of knowing and engaging in the world. The root cause of the sufferings of Vilie (before his enlightenment) and Zote lies in their stoic subscription to a notion of home that is territorial and located inside the village of their birth and childhood. Against both and in contrast to this epistemic constriction in the imagination of home, Kire portrays Ate as possessing a mobile notion of home that resembles the Nepali couple’s nomadism. In fact, Ate’s perspective on the idea of home is *the* narrative mirror for Vilie for resolving his own issues – this will become clearer later.

The novel opens *in media res*: “The forest was home to Vilie” (3). We know from the text that the forest is not Vilie’s natal home. He had relocated there when he was twenty-five years old. At the physical level, Vilie’s choice of the forest as home is an obvious deviation from the cultural norm of the Nagas. It is an uncommon example of inversion of the locus of one’s habitation with the field of one’s operation. For the typical Naga, home in the village is the starting point for activity in the world. It is the reference point when he is far away in the forest or in an unknown land. It constitutes the “homeworld” in relation to the “alienworld” in Husserl’s conception of lived reality.¹⁶ The village traditionally represents a familiar,

¹⁶From Husserl’s conception of “lifeworld” in *The Crisis of European Sciences and Transcendental Phenomenology: An Introduction to Phenomenological Philosophy*, 1970 (1930). Translated into English from the German original by David Carr.

sanitised, and safe space for dwelling – notionally off-limits for malignant spirits, human enemies, and wild animals. However, in Vilie’s case, the forest, associated with ideas of the wild and the unpredictable, is converted into the reference point from which he engages with human society. He visits the village and the marketplace only when he needs salt, oil, and other edible items not easily found in the forest, and when his job as a Forest Ranger requires it – Vilie’s job as a Forest Ranger is not the cause of his relocation to the forest though. It is as if Vilie wants to return to life in its simplest form to avoid the emotional and psychological entanglements of human society. He appears to be more open to the possibility of physical harm (in the forest) than live according to the social norms and etiquettes *inside* a village community.¹⁷ He is a curious anomaly, begging psychological questions about his past and present. Even though the text is not explicit about Vilie’s reason(s) for relocating to the forest, two events are implied as probable causes. When he was eighteen, Mechuseno, the woman he loved, was taken by a forest spirit (4-6). Shortly after, he lost his mother (141). Two women that Vilie adored, and around whom he seems to have built his purpose in life, left him one after another. At the time of the novel’s opening, these events had become memories from more than twenty years ago. However, despite the passage of time, Vilie has not been able to find closure for his grief and persistent state of unquiet. The relocation to the forest only mitigated the pain without real healing. A cognitive-emotional barrier seems to restrict his attempt to reach a state of emotional and physical equilibrium:

And you buried your mother in that village and made the forest your home, but you always think of that village where your mother is buried as home, your real home, and you long to go back, at least in your dreams if not in your waking moments (141).

¹⁷ “Inside” connotes a more territorial notion of belonging or residence in the village, which is the idea here. “Within” is less territorial in its connotation, and can extend to spaces outside the village. Vilie, in that sense, is still *within* the village – its norms and social epistemology apply; but he is physically located *outside* the village, which spares him from performing the daily interpersonal etiquettes expected *inside* the village.

Vilie's move away from the site of pain, the village, is both symptomatic and necessary. The idea that moving away from the site of pain/trauma can aid recovery or healing of the subject is not uncommon in care psychology. So, Vilie's relocation to the forest is understandable, and perhaps even worth recommending – for the text tells us he loves the forest. In another sense, the physical flight from the village can be read as symptomatic of the degree of his grief, and his inability to deal with it. It is suggestive of the fact that he lacked friends who could have stepped in to provide him with the emotional support to deal with his grief – the text is silent about his friends, but mentions two spinster-aunts. Vilie seems to have essentially centred his life in the village around two women: his mother and Mechuseno. And when one passed, the presence of the other was adequate for him to still remain in the village. However, when the second woman also departed, he found no pleasure and purpose in remaining in the village. It is like the life source of his existence was removed. The village space now, once shared with them, reminded him of what he had lost, and perhaps, what his life could have been with them still living in it. It is as if Vilie saw the village as a mere stage on which the principal actors, his mother and Mechuseno, were supposed to help him fulfil his destiny. So, without them, the play came undone, and he sought to look for his destiny elsewhere. The forest became his new stage-home. But this too was not carefully thought out, as he is once again pushed to the edge of the stage. The unhappiness arising from these events places Vilie in a position suitable for the novel's *bildung* scheme: the path to discovery and self-enlightenment.

Within the *bildung* scheme, the protagonist usually leaves behind a sort of developmental curve for the reader to trace. At the start of *WTRS*, Villie is already beset with

a gnawing existential crisis for two years. Even though the narrator tells us that Vilie was relatively “content with how things were” (in the forest), the textual evidence says otherwise (4). The opening paragraph of the novel tells us that Vilie is bothered by something that he is unable to articulate:

Vilie plunged his hand into the river. It was cold – close to freezing – and perfectly still. It was just the way it should be. The river had gone to sleep. Everything was just as the seer had told him. Almost imperceptibly, he slid forward and entered the water and plucked a smooth stone from the bottom of the river. In a similar motion, he pulled his arm out of the water and stood still. But it was too late. He felt through the soles of his feet that a great force had awakened. Before he could reach the shore, the water had swelled above his waist – the river had come alive! In an instant, the great torrents had tethered his legs in its twisting undercurrents, dragging him down forcibly into its depths. Vilie’s struggles were feeble against the force of the rushing water. Unable to reach the surface, his lungs began to burn for air and his mouth filled with water. He tried to shout, even as he felt himself being swallowed further into the darkness. Above his struggling form the river roared, drowning out his muffled screams. Then, in a final panicked outburst, he struck out against the power that was consuming him. His movements grew more frantic. A deep guttural sound escaped his throat. He flung out his hand and it hit the edge of the bed. It then dawned on him that he had been dreaming again (1-2).

The “cause” of this crisis appears quite tame and ordinary, for who would have thought a recurring dream, however dark or ominous, could induce our protagonist into a state of perpetual anxiety. In a sense, Vilie’s situation is a classic example of T.S. Eliot’s *objective*

*correlative*¹⁸ - mismatch between (observed) cause and effect. But of course, the processes of psychology are not always the same in both degree and type from one to another individual, so Vilie's could have many layers beyond that which are embedded and vaguely articulated in the text. The recurring dream of wresting a heartstone from the mythical sleeping river is a subconscious projection, in the Freudian sense, of Vilie's desire to alleviate his present suffering, which a change of home has not fully remedied. Nevertheless, that desire is never fully articulated in the text. Instead, it is vaguely implied and left to the reader to infer from Vilie's emotional and physical circumstances.

So far as Vilie's intention about the heartstone is concerned, the text does not clarify it nor externalise it. Yet, the stone's value would not be unknown to Vilie. Like all Angamis, the tribe to which he belongs, Vilie would share the belief that the heartstone is capable of a range of powers:

If you can wrest a stone from the heart of the sleeping river and take it home, it will grant you whatever it is empowered to grant you. It could be cattle, women, prowess in war, or success in the hunt (3).

So, it would not be uncharacteristic for Vilie to expect an improved situation in his own life should he succeed at the sleeping river. Kire also presents the stone as a neutral object whose real value depends on how and to what end its possessor uses it:

The wisdom of the stone is more spiritual than physical. It helps us discover the spiritual identity that is within us, so we can use it to combat the dark forces that are always trying to control and suppress us. But men who are not initiated don't

¹⁸ T.S. Eliot, "Hamlet and His Problems", 1919.

understand this about the stone, and they try to use it to gain wealth and other material things (228).

This passive fact about the stone returns agency to the possessor, making the characters the site of moral and ethical actions. And by emphasising the intangible aspect of the stone, its capacity to give wisdom to the honest seeker in difficult situations, Kire alludes to the nature of Vilie's problem as one that arises chiefly from *spiritual* bankruptcy.¹⁹

In one of the stops on his return from the sleeping river with the heartstone, Vilie runs into the village of Kirhupfümia, where the sisters, Ate and Zote, dwell.²⁰ Kire achieves two things by causing the protagonist to inhabit the same space as two other principal characters. First, she demonstrates the working of the stone and its range of powers, as Vilie and Zote employ it differently; second, the question of home is more directly addressed through their motives and actions. All three characters are estranged from their natal village and have different notions of home. However, the circumstances of their estrangement are not similar: Vilie chose to relocate to the forest of his own accord, but the two sisters were ostracised because they were considered to be witches. Structurally, if the wresting of the stone from the sleeping river is the apogee of the narrative, then this encounter with the two sisters is the start of the resolution. Subsequently, Vilie becomes more precise and decisive in his thought and deeds. He is also able to articulate clearly his reason for choosing the forest for his home.

¹⁹ Kire's concept of "spiritual" is irreligious, even though it is imbued with moral and ethical duties.

²⁰ "Kirhupfümia" is the Angami term for certain women believed to be born with poisonous powers. Anything they point at with their fingers and with intent to hurt or with malice suffers pain, and even death, in humans/beings, and wither and death in plants.

Zote

Zote represents a territorial understanding of home, where primacy is accorded to the physical space of one's natal village. Zote's relentless hatred for her village is fundamentally grounded in this psychosocial logic of Naga lifeworld. Even though the text mentions that the village had mistreated Zote, it nonetheless portrays her as resentful, evil, and craving revenge (135-136). The text also gives the impression that Zote's reaction, or desire for revenge, is the result of giving in to the dark forces at work in her heart. However, when Zote's revenge motive is examined more closely, another factor emerges, displacing, or rivalling at least, righteous indignation, or dark forces, as the fundamental cause. In fact, this factor is not even obvious to Zote herself, nor to Ate and Vilie for that matter. The surface manifestations of bitterness, rage, and desire for revenge disguise deeper psychological and cognitive issues, which I would argue, are the cause of Zote's destabilised action.

Zote's action results from emotional instability caused principally by inadequacy of cognition – of her situation. She takes her ostracism from the village *personally* and refuses to move on. Zote is fully aware that the practice of expelling a known *kirhupfü* (witches) from the village is common among the Angami Nagas. She was not the first *kirhupfü* to be expelled in this way, nor would she be the last. As such, her extremely adverse reaction cannot be understood as arising entirely from moral indignation caused by injustice. Underneath her seemingly righteous indignation is an inability to imagine home differently from the traditional, territorial model. Consequently, Zote is unable to move on and instead takes the folk belief personally as *her* fight. In that sense, Zote's fight is not only against her natal village; it is also against a custom in the Angami traditional belief system. Her death at the hands of the ancestor-spirits is suggestive of the nature of her fight. In fact, the

appearance of the ancestor-spirits to defend the village from Zote's violence signifies the restoration of the disrupted status quo, wherein the tradition of expelling any known *kirhupfü* from the village will continue. Zote's regret, rendered movingly towards the end of chapter thirty-nine, then is not so much about losing her life as about the manner in which she lost it and, with it, her sister and the *kirhupfümia* community. In the knowing words of Ate: "I know now for sure that she regretted doing what she did, and that she met her death through it. I know she grieves losing me"(167).

At another level of signification, Zote's premature end is not so much about the triumph of tradition as it is about Kire's subtle emphasis on the willingness to accept new realities and adjust the structures of meaning to survive and even thrive. Was a relatively normal life possible for Zote in a new village? The change in Ate's fortune is Kire's answer to the question. Should we then avoid confronting oppressive traditional practices? The text does not advocate an answer in the affirmative nor castigate folk beliefs in general. However, it would seem fair to say that adopting Zote's way of confronting oppressive folk beliefs should be avoided. Instead, a more delicate and circumspect manner of confronting is poignantly suggested through Ate's happy ending. One might argue that Zote is not the average Naga with a traditional notion of home. But she certainly represents one end of the epistemic spectrum.

Ate

At the other end of the home spectrum is Zote's younger sister, Ate, who has accepted and made her peace with the arbitrary banishment from the village. She confesses to Vilie:

This is my home. I feel home here where there are none to judge me or to spy on me and accuse me of things I am not guilty of. Here, there is no one to say that I caused a bad harvest or that I brought hail and lightning to destroy crops of my neighbours. I don't hanker to go back. I was quite young when I left. I have no pleasant memories of my ancestral village that I should want to go back to it (142-143).

At age nine, Ate was expelled from the village along with her sister Zote for being born as “witches”. The passage quoted above indicates that Ate did have a rough childhood in her natal village. She attributes her lack of desire to return to the absence of “pleasant memories” about the natal village. Typically, regardless of the quality of life, a Naga village girl would have developed some form of attachment to her home and village by age nine. This is engendered by the fact that the *territoriality* of the village space is indispensable to the traditional Naga conception of home (and identity). So, even though the narrative suggests it, age is unlikely to be a significant contributory factor in Ate's indifference towards her natal village. Instead, what comes through as the cause of her peace in contrast to Zote's bitterness and anger is her attitude to *what* constitutes home. Compelled to live in the village of Kirhupfümia, Ate develops an attitude that allows her to find relative contentment in her new surroundings: “With time...she had embraced her new life in the village of the Kirhupfümia”(168). The hopeful acceptance of her new situation and the experience of relative happiness in limited circumstances combine to produce an unintentional effect: destabilise the traditional notion of the Nagas that a home can be found *only* inside a village. Instead, the *affective* aspects of home, like the quality of life, for instance, are given more importance in the emerging home discourse in the novel. Consequently, Ate does not mind

leaving her natal home as it can never provide her with the dignity and freedom she now enjoys in the outcast-village of Kirhupfūmia.

Vilie would seem to share a similar attitude with Ate going by the passage cited in the previous paragraph – the deaths of his mother and Mechuseno rendered the village emotionally unviable. But there is a *qualitative* difference, in that Vilie was not without “pleasant memories” of his village in the manner Ate characterises her memory of her birthplace. Nonetheless, the freedom condition of home, on which Vilie would pivot his decision later on, underlines Ate’s articulation of her notion of home. In abstract terms, Ate has reconceived and rearranged the basic components of home according to their importance. Unlike Zote, the physical space of the village is not as important to her as the people who make up the community. Zote’s attachment to her natal village is stronger than Ate’s despite the greater scorn she faced there before their ostracism (132). However, to Ate the quality of experience is fundamental in thinking of home and belonging. The physical house is an important component, for the spirit of home needs the body of the house, so to speak, but Ate represents a model of home that is moveable; a model that is aligned with Rushdie’s mental concept, and which is essentially dependent on the effect produced by the place.²¹ In short, Ate’s notion of home is premised on the idea that the physical house is dispensable. So, when it became necessary, she has no trouble abandoning her second home in the village of Kirhupfūmia as well.²²

²¹ Salman Rushdie, *Imaginary Homelands: Essays and Criticism 1981-1991*. 1991.

²² Kire’s other protagonist, Pele, in *Son of the Thundercloud*, also demonstrates a similar condition-based nomadism in his conception of home – or where to build a home.

Generally, Naga identity is tied to the village of birth and the tribe. These larger categories of selfhood tend to subsume individual subjectivities and influence one's perception of home and the world. In Veio Pou's *Waiting for the Dust to Settle* (2020), Rakovei's existential crisis can be traced to his inability to assimilate the new experience of Naga modernity with traditional Naga ethos concerning home and village – Rakovei occupies three “homes” in Senapati town, Phyamaichi village, and Delhi one after another. The sacrosanctity of the village space (and its violation by the counterinsurgency actions of the Indian state) is also the cultural context for the stories in Temsula Ao's *These Hills Called Home*. However, Kire's Ate breaks from tradition, perhaps signifying a new attitude of attachment to the village space in millennial Naga culture: “If I am going to start a new life, why should I take so much of the old with me? It would only hinder me from beginning my new existence” (170). She is aware of the complications of looking back too often, symbolised by the material items she chooses to leave behind, and the will that is required to make a new start possible. The new life will not be a *tabula rasa*, as the memories of the old will continue to linger. But a conception of life as a journey that passes through different points in time is underscored; and at each stop, there is a choice not to be trapped in the past like Zote – also a theme Kire explores in *Bitter Wormwood*.

Ate's decision to follow Vilie to his village after the strange disappearance of the inhabitants of Kirhupfūmia is crucial for resolving Vilie's problem. Ate's positive attitude despite the uncertainty surrounding her future functions as a narratorial mirror for Vilie to put his own situation in perspective: “Vilie marvelled at the wisdom of the young woman” (170). From being unable to deal with his own grief in chapter one, Vilie grows into a man who can and wants to help those around him by the close of the novel. Redeeming Ate is a key

example of his development as a person: calling the lie that she is cursed (136-139), helping her find her third home (223), and ultimately sacrificing his life for her (229-230). In fact, his sacrifice at the end to protect Ate and the orphaned Nepali child, both of whom share no blood ties with him, is not easily placeable within traditional Naga ethos of duties of parent to child. Of course, it may be argued that Vilie had adopted them so it is a natural response of a parent to protect their ward(s). But the narrative does not seem to stress so much on the *adoption* part as it does on Vilie's transformation into the best version of himself – thanks to the power of the heartstone! In that sense, Vilie can be said to have attained a level of humanism that transcends the particularity of the Naga traditional culture and lifeworld.

Conclusion

The forest is retained as the locus of Vilie's dwelling in the end. But unlike in the past, he is now able to clearly articulate his reason for the unusual choice of the forest for his home: "I will not come back to live here. I am too used to the freedom that my forest life offers" (224). There is a paradigmatic shift in his articulation that was absent when the novel began. His initial relocation to the forest was more of a flight from an unhappy situation than the conscious decision of an adult. His renewed choice of the forest as home though is rooted in a teleology of home, in which freedom is both indispensable and the principal determinant. In other words, Vilie's choice to keep operating from his home in the forest, even though he now has parental duties towards Ate and the orphaned Nepali infant in the village, is not an escape from a situation that he cannot handle. Rather, it exemplifies the confidence and capability of a man who can meaningfully balance his individual life with his parental duties. In reiterating the value of freedom in this conception of home, Kire draws attention to a commonly overlooked aspect in traditional Naga notion of home. If home is where the heart

is, surely the heart must be where freedom is most found. The physical house and the village, though important, are no longer *the* defining attributes of home.

References

Ao, Temsula. *These Hills Called Home: Stories from a War Zone*. New Delhi, Penguin India, 2005.

------. *Laburnum for my Head*. New Delhi, Penguin India, 2009.

Baishya, A. R., & Moral, R. K. “‘Insides-Outsides’: Northeast Indian Anglophone Literature.” *South Asian Review*, 44 (3–4), Dec. 2023, pp.180–190.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02759527.2023.2255045>

Barthes, Roland. “The Death of the Author.” *Image, Music, Text*. Translated by Stephen Heath, Hill & Wang, 1977, pp. 142-148.

Beteille, Andre. “The Idea of Indigenous People.” *Current Anthropology*, Vol. 9, No. 2, April 1998, pp. 187-192.

Burke, Sean. *The Death and Return of the Author. Criticism and Subjectivity in Barthes, Foucault, and Derrida*. Edinburgh University Press, 2008.

Casavi, Thejalkhoukho. “Reading *A Country with No Home*”. *Nagaland Post*, 21 August 2024, <https://nagalandpost.com/index.php/2024/08/21/reading-a-country-with-no-home/>

Das, N.K. “Indigeneity, Anthropology and the Indian Tribes: A Critique.” *Journal of Adivasi and Indigenous Tribes*, Vol. II, No. I, Feb. 2015, pp.11-34.

Geertz, Clifford. *The Interpretation of Cultures*. Basic Books, 1973.

Eliot, Thomas Stearns. "Hamlet and His Problems." *The Sacred Wood*. Alfred A. Knopf, 1921.

Bartleby.com, <https://www.bartleby.com/lit-hub/the-sacred-wood/hamlet-and-his-problems/>

Husserl, Edmund. *The Crisis of European Sciences and Transcendental Phenomenology: An Introduction to Phenomenological Philosophy*. Translated by David Carr, Northwestern University Press, 1970 (1930).

Iralu, Easterine. *A Naga Village Remembered*. Kohima, Ura Academy, 2003.

Irwin, William (ed.). *The Death and Resurrection of the Author*. Connecticut, Greenwood Press, 2002.

Kamei, Achingliu. "An Ecocritical Study of Easterine Kire's *When The River Sleeps* and *Son of the Thundercloud*." *Keeper of Stories: Critical Readings of Easterine Kire's Novels*, edited by Veio Pou, Maine, Highlander, 2023, pp.201-214.

Khumbah, Lozaan. *A Country With no Home: Poems from JNU*. Kohima, PenThrill Publications, 2024.

Kire, Easterine. *A Terrible Matriarchy*. New Delhi, Zubaan, 2007.

----- . *Mari*. New Delhi, HarperCollins, 2010.

----- . *Bitter Wormwood*. New Delhi, Zubaan, 2011.

----- . *When the River Sleeps*. New Delhi, Zubaan, 2014.

----- . *Son of the Thundercloud*. New Delhi, Speaking Tiger, 2016.

----- . *Journey of the Stone*. Norway, Barkweaver Publications, 2021.

----- . *Spirit Night*. Plymouth, Barbican Press, 2022.

Menezes, Vivek. "Naga Writer Easterine Kire's Clear Bright Sound Over a Sleeping World."

Scroll, 20 May 2021, <https://scroll.in/article/995300/naga-writer-easterine-kires-clear-bright-sound-over-a-sleeping-world>

- Pou, Veio. *Literary Cultures of India's Northeast: Naga Writings in English*. Dimapur, Heritage Publishing House, 2015.
- . *Waiting for the Dust to Settle*. New Delhi, Speaking Tiger, 2020.
- Rushdie, Salman. *Imaginary Homelands: Essays and Criticism 1981-1991*. London, Penguin Books, 1991.
- Wijunamai, Roderick. "Understanding Naga Cosmology Through Easterine Kire's Fictional Narratives." *Keeper of Stories: Critical Readings of Easterine Kire's Novels*, edited by Veio Pou, Maine, Highlander, 2023, pp. 29-42.
- Willingham, John. "The New Criticism: Then and Now." In *Contemporary Literary Theory*, edited by Douglas Atkins and Janice Morrow. University of Massachusetts Press, 1989, pp. 24-41.
- Xaxa, Virginius. "Tribes as Indigenous People of India." *Economic and Political Weekly*, Vol. 34, No. 51, Dec. 18-24, 1999, pp. 3589-3595.